

nuSCOPE: a monitored and tagged neutrino beam for high-precision neutrino interaction measurements

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Neutrino physics is entering its precision era!

- The next generation of long-baseline neutrino experiments will aim to **precisely** measure neutrino oscillations parameters and CP violation.

Experiment	ν_μ events	ν_e events	Syst. error
	318	94	~ 5 %
	384	181	~ 5 %

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	318	94	~ 5 %
	384	181	~ 5 %
	~ 9000	~ 2500	Need 1-3%
	~ 15000 *	~ 3500 *	Need 1-3%

* Projected to 10 years of data taking

- The next generation will aim to significantly increase the statistics... rendering systematic errors dominant!
- Leading challenges:
 - uncertainties on the neutrino flux and cross section;
 - bias on neutrino energy reconstruction.

Why it's so difficult: theoretical models

- ν -nucleus interactions in the GeV energy range involve multiple physical processes, including QE scattering, resonance production, and DIS.

arXiv:2301.03700

Phys. Rev. D 98, 032003 (2018)

- Current theoretical models are unable to describe all available neutrino scattering measurements.

Phys. Rev. Lett. 121, 022504 (2018)

Nature 599, p. 565-570 (2021)

Why it's so difficult: theoretical models

- ν -nucleus interactions in the GeV energy range + hadronization and final-state interactions in nuclear medium. Theoretical models include QE scattering, resonance production, and DIS.

+ hadronization and final-state interactions inside the nuclear medium!

- Current theoretical models are unable to describe all available neutrino scattering measurements.

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Why it's so difficult: measurements

- Unlike electron scattering experiments (known monochromatic probe energy), neutrino scattering experiments have **large flux uncertainties**.
- The unknown & broad-band flux makes it difficult to measure cross sections precisely.

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We need a change of paradigm!

nuSCOPE: a monitored & tagged neutrino beam

nuSCOPE: neutrino SPS
Complex for Precision
Experiments

ESPPU input: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2503.21589>

- **nuSCOPE** is a new facility that overcomes the limitations of conventional neutrino beams for precision cross-section measurements, formed from the merger of the **ENUBET** and **NuTAG** collaborations.
- It combines **monitoring** and **tagging** techniques to tightly constrain neutrino flux and energy in the range relevant to next-generation oscillation experiments.

nuSCOPE: a monitored & tagged neutrino beam

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Complex for Precision
Experiments

- Monitoring consists of **instrumenting the decay tunnel & the hadron dump**, and by detecting and counting the decay products of mesons producing neutrinos

ENUBET demonstrator of the instrumented decay tunnel

- **Shielding:**
 - 30 cm of borated polyethylene;
 - SiPMs installed on top give an 18-times reduction in neutron fluence.
- Calorimeter with $e/\pi/\mu$ separation capabilities:
 - sampling calorimeter: sandwich of plastic scintillators and iron absorbers;
 - three radial layers of modules / longitudinal segmentation;
 - WLS-fibers/SiPMs for light collection/readout.
- Photon-veto for π^0 rejection and timing:
 - plastic scintillator tiles arranged in doublets forming inner rings with a time resolution of ~ 400 ps.

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+ PID based on the pattern of energy deposit in the calorimeter module

nuSCOPE: a monitored & tagged neutrino beam

nuSCOPE: neutrino SPS Complex for Precision Experiments

- The tagging will be performed thanks to state-of-the-art silicon detectors that track incoming mesons & outgoing muons; this will give us a unique association between each neutrino interacting in the detector and its parents

The NA62 GigaTracker: a low mass high intensity beam 4D tracker with 65 ps time resolution on tracks [[arXiv:1904.12837](https://arxiv.org/abs/1904.12837)]

nuSCOPE: a monitored & tagged neutrino beam

nuSCOPE: neutrino SPS
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- The tagging of the beam with mesons & other particles is a unique associated with neutrinos interacting in the detector and its parents

Neutrino tagging with these detectors was demonstrated by NA62: see “First detection of a tagged neutrino in the NA62 experiment” [[arXiv:2412.04033](https://arxiv.org/abs/2412.04033)] and M. Perrin-Terrin’s [talk](#) at NuPhys 2023

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Tagging

Important challenge for tracking: particle rates

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Peak rate: ~ 0.6 MHz/mm²

Requirements for these measurements

- For these measurements to be possible, we need:
 - slow extraction

Parameter	Value
Primary proton momentum (GeV/c)	400
Beamline meson momentum (GeV/c)	max. 8.5
Proton-beam spill duration	slow (4.8 s to 9.6 s)
Spill intensity (protons/spill)	1×10^{13}
Event rate (THz)	1 – 2
Instantaneous power on target (W)	170 – 340
(K^+, π^+) yield per proton	$(1.3 \times 10^{-3}, 1.9 \times 10^{-2})$
(K^+, π^+) rate (GHz)	max. (2.7, 40)
Annual proton intensity (protons/year)	$2.1\text{--}3.2 \times 10^{18}$
Total proton requirement (protons)	1.4×10^{19}

POTs allow for full compatibility with SPS program!

Requirements for these measurements

- For these measurements to be possible, we need:
 - slow extraction
 - very precise silicon detectors

Specifications [units]	Beam Spectro.	Muon Spectro.
Peak Dose [Mrad]	700	60
Peak Fluence [$1\text{MeVn}_{\text{eq}}/\text{cm}^2$]	1×10^{16}	6×10^{14}
Peak Rate [MHz/mm^2]	20	0.6
Time Resolution [ps]	< 40	< 100
Pixel Pitch [μm]	300	
Material Budget [X_0]	< 1%	

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Total proton requirement (protons)			

- to compensate for the loss in neutrino beam intensity with a large detector [$O(1 \text{ kt})$]

What physics measurements
can we perform with nuSCOPE?

Setup for the studies

Studies done assuming 1.4×10^{19} POT (5 years of running, POT to ensure compatibility with fixed target experiments e.g. SHiP)

- Current studies are preliminary and have been performed using a simple detector design; reference model is GENIE AR23_20i_00_000.
- The low beam intensity is compensated by large detector size & proximity to beam
- Monitoring performance:
 - $O(1.0 \times 10^6)$ / $O(1.2 \times 10^4)$ monitored ν_μ / ν_e CC events in LAr and water
- Tagging performance:
 - 7.6×10^5 tagged ν_μ CC events in LAr (500t)
 - 1.4×10^5 tagged ν_μ CC events in water (100t), of which 52k tagged ν_μ CC0 π events

Tagged rate & mis-tagging probability

Neutrino energy reconstruction

- Neutrino energy is reconstructed from observed final-state particles.
- Tagged neutrinos in **nuSCOPE** provide samples with known true energy, independent of detector response, enabling direct studies of calorimetric energy reconstruction under realistic conditions.

Energy dependence of the cross-section

- We can measure ν -N CC cross-sections as a function of E_ν .

Measuring the energy bias

- Independent knowledge of the neutrino energy enables event-by-event comparison of reconstructed and true energy.
- nuSCOPE measures absolute and relative energy bias as a function of neutrino energy and interaction channel, providing experimental sensitivity to nuclear effects and invisible energy losses that dominate systematics.

$$E_{\nu}^{\text{reco}} = E_{\mu} + \sum_{i=\pi^{\pm}, p} T_i + \sum_{i=\pi^0, \gamma} E_i$$

Electron scattering-like measurements

- The neutrino energy is known event-by-event...
- We can thus study the dynamics of nuclear effects!

Possible implementation at CERN

- The implementation of the facility in the CERN complex is being studied in the framework of the Physics Beyond Collider (PBC) program; proton sharing is compatible with other fixed target experiments.

Two sites identified:

- ECN4, in the Prévessin campus
- LSS6, close to HighRadMat in the Meyrin campus (current preferred option)

• Project status & roadmap

- 2024–2025: Input to ESPPU (featured in the Physics Briefing Book)
 - Beamline design, initial physics sensitivities
- Oct. 2025 (CERN): Workshop & collaboration kick-off
 - Neutrino detector design and physics studies
- Ongoing: Advanced simulation & reconstruction framework
- Near-term: Letter of Intent submission to CERN SPSC

• Next steps

- Detector technologies under study: water Cherenkov, liquid argon (LAr)
- Silicon tracker R&D inspired by HL-LHC
 - Possible technologies: TIMESPOT, PicoPix
- Expanded physics program
- Precision cross sections
- BSM searches: sterile neutrinos
- Muon and kaon physics (large fluxes of both)

- Achieving an order-of-magnitude improvement in our understanding of ν cross sections at the GeV scale is crucial for fully exploiting the physics reach of next-gen oscillation experiments.
- From the work of the **ENUBET** and **NuTAG** collaborations, the techniques for monitoring and tagging have reached a high level of maturity.
- We are therefore able to put forward a new facility aimed at addressing this challenge with **percent-level accuracy**, with the intention of realizing it at CERN (can run compatibly with other planned CERN projects - mostly SHIP).
- The scientific motivation is strong, and ongoing studies continue to broaden and refine the scope of its physics case.
- While the underlying technologies are largely ready, important open issues remain, particularly concerning integration at CERN, precise meson tracking, and neutrino detection with sub-nanosecond timing resolution.

**Thanks for the
attention!**

from the nuSCOPE workshop held at CERN last October (<https://indico.cern.ch/event/1548855/>)

Backup

Conventional neutrino beams

- Van der Meer paradigm: Employ the most intense proton accelerator at your disposal → Focus as many pions/kaons as possible → Eliminate any material along the beamline in the decay tunnel → Build the largest possible neutrino detector

Pros:

- Large yield of pions per POTs;
- Large number of neutrinos from pion decay;
- Large statistics of neutrino interaction events (CC and NC)

Cons:

- Lack of control on neutrino energy
- Coarse beam diagnostics
- Limited precision in the final state reconstruction

Monitored & tagged neutrino beams

Pros:

- We select secondaries in a narrow energy band
- We can track pions at single particle level using fast silicon tracker (tagging)
- We can measure charged leptons associated with the neutrino decay (direct monitoring of flux)
- Exquisite reconstruction of interaction vertex and final state particles
- Time correlation with parent pion and daughter muon (tagging)

Cons:

- Limited neutrino beam intensity
- Need for fast, rad-hard detectors
- Limited statistics

Beamline parameters

- Beamline parameters and specifications of the newly optimized nuSCOPE beamline at SPS energies. The total proton requirement targets a 1% statistical uncertainty on the inclusive ν_e cross-section.

[arXiv:2503.21589v2](https://arxiv.org/abs/2503.21589v2)

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Primary proton momentum (GeV/c)	400
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Proton-beam spill duration	slow (4.8 s to 9.6 s)
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Total proton requirement (protons)	1.4×10^{19}

Beamline

Design	Done	Possible improvement in reduction of non-monitored neutrinos
Components	Done	Standard components
Slow extraction	In progress	Depends on final implementation
Infrastructure	In progress	//

Diagnostics for lepton monitoring/tagging

Decay tunnel instrumentation	Done	ENUBET R&D (2016-2022)
Hadron dump	In progress	ENUBET+PIMENT R&D (2021-ongoing)
Silicon tracking panels	In R&D	Technologies not yet fully validated
Outer tracking planes & muon spectrometer	In progress	Design and validation in progress

Neutrino detectors

Liquid argon	In progress	Based on ProtoDUNE technologies with enhanced light detection (Run 3)
Water Cherenkov - WBLS	Done	Based on WCTE's technology or Water Based Liquid Scintillators
Muon catcher and cosmic ray veto	In progress	Depends on final implementation

Possible implementation at CERN

- ECN4 (North Area, Preveessin):
 - A dedicated experimental hall provides greater flexibility for detector installation and the addition of new detectors for cross-section studies with specific targets. 😊
 - Slow extraction is already implemented in LSS2. 😊
 - The beam splitter presents significant technical challenges. 😞
 - Neutrino detectors have minimal overburden, leading to increased cosmic ray background during long extractions. 😞
 - May require a dedicated cycle for nuSCOPE, potentially increasing the impact on proton availability for other experiments. 😞
- TNC/TT61/TCC6 (East Area, Meyrin) – currently our favorite option:
 - Detectors are located underground 😊
 - Minimal interference with proton sharing among fixed target experiments 😊
 - Requires enlargement of existing tunnels to accommodate neutrino detectors. 😞
 - Implementation of a non-local slow extraction is needed. 😞

Requirements for tagging

[arXiv:2503.21589v2](https://arxiv.org/abs/2503.21589v2)

Specifications [units]	Beam Spectro.	Muon Spectro.	LHCb-VELO (2028)	NA62-GTK (since 2014)
Peak Dose [Mrad]	700	60	$> 10^3$	16
Peak Fluence [$1\text{MeV}n_{\text{eq}}/\text{cm}^2$]	1×10^{16}	6×10^{14}	5×10^{16}	4.5×10^{14}
Peak Rate [MHz/mm ²]	20	0.6	10 – 100	2
Time Resolution [ps]	< 40	< 100	< 50	< 130
Pixel Pitch [μm]	300		45	300
Material Budget [X_0]	$< 1\%$		0.8%	0.5%

Tracker specifications of the beam and muon spectrometers compared to the present NA62 Gigatracker and the future upgraded LHCb VELO.

Energy dependence of cross-section - monitoring

- By exploiting NBOA fluxes, flux-averaged cross-sections can be measured in narrow energy intervals.
- This allows the study of the energy dependence of interaction cross sections in the 1-10 GeV range.

ν_e flux measurement

- The total neutrino flux is computed as the neutrinos in the detector acceptance and then normalized to the neutrino detector $4 \times 4 \text{ m}^2$ front face area and to the total POT exposure (1.4×10^{19} POT).

NC π^0 measurement

- We can precisely measure NC π^0 production (dominant background to ν_e appearance measurements, where photons from π^0 decay can mimic electrons). Using a monitored neutrino beam + NBOA technique extends existing NC π^0 measurements beyond the sub-GeV regime.

